

Spatial Modeling Of Geomorphological Risks For Morphodynamic Processes In Haditha Region, Western Iraq

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Modeling, Geomorphological Risks, Morphodynamic Processes, Haditha</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6249723</p>	<p><i>The research dealt with the study of geomorphological risks in Haditha region based on modern technologies, as it was relied on a number of criteria and indicators by which it possible to determine the levels of risk for the morphodynamic processes represented by layers of (rock formations, linear structures, elevations, slopes, natural vegetation, and rain) and giving each layer it's importance according to the degree of impact, and through which a model for these layers was made that contains three levels of risk, represented by the least dangerous lands, an area of 15.2, while medium-risk lands formed a percentage of (82.6), while the most dangerous areas amounted to (2.2) of total area.</i></p>

Introduction

The study of geomorphological risks is an important topic; This is because of its dangerous impact on human activities and human life and the loss of life and property it causes. These risks result from geomorphological factors and processes, whether they are geological, geomorphological or climatic, and on this basis the research topic was chosen to make a model for the geomorphological risks of morphodynamic processes in Haditha region; depending on modern technologies that remote sensing (RS) data can provide us with abundant information about the earth surface phenomena. In case these data were used in a proper way, and then conduct special operations on it based on geographic information systems (GIS).

Research problem

The research problem represented by this question: (Is it possible to employ remote sensing data and modern software in building a model of geomorphological risks for morphodynamic processes in the study area)?

Research Hypothesis:

The hypothesis represents an initial answer that expresses what the researcher believes about the effectiveness of remote sensing data in producing a model that represents the levels of risk for geomorphological processes, and accordingly these techniques have proven their usefulness in studying and determining the levels of geomorphological risks.

Research aims:

- Identifying the natural factors of the area and their impact in determining the levels of risk.
- Building a model showing the levels of geomorphological risks using remote sensing data (RS) and geographic information systems (GIS).
- The main purpose of choosing such a topic is to clarify the accuracy of using remote sensing data in determining levels of risk.

Research Methodology:

No researcher can reach results without relying on a set of principles, rules and guidelines, which represent the scientific research method, and on the basis of that the research relied on the following methods:-

The inductive and analytical approach leads to the adoption of quantitative methods and methods in the use of mathematical standards and spatial information systems software in order to build models that simulate reality to provide an analytical vision of work mechanisms.

Location and space:

The study area is located in western of Iraq within the Anbar Governorate, specifically within Haditha district. As for astronomically, it is located between two latitudes ($0^{\circ} 52' 33'' - 0^{\circ} 38' 34''$) north and between longitudes ($0^{\circ} 0' 42'' - 0^{\circ} 44' 42''$) east, see map (1), as for its area, it reached (3214.36) km²..

Data sources, visuals and modern computer software used in the study:

- 1-Topographical map of Iraq at a scale of 1:100000 for the year 1990 issued by the General area Association.
- 2- The map of Iraq and Al-Anbar Administrative Governorate, year 2020, scale 1:100000
- 3- A satellite image of the satellite (Landsat 8), captured on February 22, 2021.
- 4- Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30 x 30) meters for the year 2000.
- 5- Arc GIS 10.8 program to derive and analyze data and draw maps.
- 6- Erdas Imagine 14 program to correct and integrate Land sat 8 data.
- 7-Global Mapper 12 program
- 8- Program (Google Earth).

Map (1) location of the region from Iraq

Source: From the researcher's work based on:

- Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Water Resources, General area Association, Map of Iraq and the Administrative Governorate of Anbar, for the year 2020, 1000000:1 scale.
- A topographic map of Iraq at a scale of 1:100,000 for the year 1990, issued by the General Space Association.
- Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30 x 30) meters.
- Using the program (Arc GIS 10.8).

First: Geological Formation:

The study area is located within the geologically stable kerb, and within a group of geological formations that vary in the area they cover, as the area of the Euphrates formation, which is one of the widest formations in extension by about (900.96) km², is (28%) of the region formations space, and the gab formation with an area of (852.5) km², i.e. with a percentage of the area reached (26.5%), while the sediments fill the valleys with the least formations with an area of (12.2) km², which is (0.4%) of the area of the formations in the region, see map (2) and table (1).

Map (2) Geographical distribution of geological formations in the study area

Source: The researcher's organizing based on the Ministry of Industry and Minerals, General Company for Geological Survey and Mining, Baghdad, Iraq's geological map, scale 1: 100,000, for the year 2000 AD (Arc GIS 10.8).

Table (1) The rock formations an area by km2 and percentage %

formation	Area km ²	Percentage %
Anna formation	588.9	18.3
Euphrates formation	900.96	28
Alfatha formation	852.5	26.5
Al-Nafael formation	254.7	7.9
Fluvial terraced sediments	68.9	2.1
Slopes sediments	179.7	5.6
Remaining soils	227.7	7.1
Gypsum soils	51.8	1.6
Flood Plain Sediments	77	2.5
Valley Filling Sediments	12.2	0.4
Total	3214.36 km ²	100%

Source: based on map (2) and using the program (Arc GIS10.8).

Second: Linear Compositions :

They are linear or straight natural phenomena of geological origin that can be observed through visuals Satellite images, or aerial photographs, or the appearance of valley streams in straight, striking shapes. They are areas of rocky weakness in the rock layers of faults and breaks, and the adjacent linear structures vary based on length and direction and may reflect geological movements present under the surface of the earth, and linear structures have an important role in the morphodynamic processes and the stability of materials on the slopes, as it is a

direct factor for the instability of the region in which they appear. And it helps in activating the processes of weathering and erosion (geological weakness areas) that cause the movement of terrestrial materials (morphodynamic processes), as they can be studied through the following:-

Linear structures with north-south direction:

The number of these structures reached (18) linear structures, which amounted to (21.9%) of the total region structures. As for the lengths of these structures, they reached (73.1) km out of the total lengths of the structures amounting to (348.2) km, and thus the rate reached (20.9%). From the ratio of structures, see Map (3).

Linear structures with north-east-southwest direction:

Their number reached (21) linear structures, and their percentage reached (25.6%) of the total repeats of structures in the study area, see table (2), as for their lengths, they reached (107.1) km out of the total lengths of structures amounting to (348.2) km, forming a percentage of (30.7%) of the total proportion of those structures.

Linear structures with an east-west direction:

Their number was (9) linear structures and (11%) of the total repetitions of the prevailing structures, and their lengths reached (55.9) km out of the total lengths of (348.2) km, and their percentage was (16.2%) of the structures.

Linear structures with a direction northwest – southeast:

Their number was (34) linear structures, constituting (41.5%) of the total frequency of linear structures in the study area, as for their lengths, they reached (112.1) km out of the total lengths of (348.2) km, forming a percentage of 32.1% of the percentage of linear structures of the study area.

Map (3) linear structures in the study area

Source: Based on the satellite visualization of the study area (Land Sat 8) for the year 2019 AD and using the programs (Erdas8.4), (Geomatica 2015) and (Arc GIS10.8).

Table (2) . Directions, lengths, recurrence and percentage of linear structures(%)in the study area
Source: Based on map (3).

Direction of linear structures	Structure lengths (km)	Percentage (%)	Directional numerical recurrence	Percentage (%)
North – South	73.1	20.9	18	21.9
Northeast – Southwest	107.1	30.8	21	25.6
East – West	55.9	16.2	9	11
Northwest – Southeast	112.1	32.1	34	41.5
Total	348.2	100%	82	100%

Density of linear structures:

Through the use of the program (Arc GIS 10.8) and through the (density) command, the study area was divided into three areas according to their numerical density per square kilometer within the area, see map (4), which are:

Low-density areas: the space of areas with less than one combination per square kilometer is about (86.3%) of the total area.

Medium-density areas: the space of areas in which there are (2.5-4 combinations) per square kilometer is about (3.9%) of the total area.

Highly density areas: the space of areas in which there are more than (8.5) composition per square kilometer is about (9.8) of the total area.

We conclude from the foregoing that the area where the linear structures increase in density is geologically weak area; Which makes it less resistance to weathering and erosion factors, causing the activity of morphodynamic processes on the lopes foot ; Thus, it causes a great danger to its inhabitants, and this is the opposite of what happens in the area with less linear structures.

Map (4) Density of linear structures for the study area

Source: Based on the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30×30 m) and the satellite visual (Land Sat 8) for the year 2019 AD and using the programs (Arc GIS10.8), (Erdas8.4) and (Geomatica 2015).

Stability of linear structures:

Linear structures have a clear impact on the processes of weathering and erosion, and their relationship to the morphodynamic processes on the slopes, especially in areas with steep slopes, so the area was divided into three areas according to the proximity and distance from the linear structures. See map (5) and table(3).

Unstable areas: The areas that are far from the linear structures by less than 1.3km. Their space is about (114.6) km², which forms (3.6%) of the study area. They are have the lowest percentage among the rest of the species within the region, and is distributed near the Euphrates River and the Al-Ssad area.

Semi-stable: The areas that are far from the linear structures by more than 1.3 - 2.7 km and its space is (183.2) km², which forms about (5.7%) of the study area.

Stable areas: The areas that are far from the linear structures by more than 2.8 km and it's space is (2916.6 km²), which forms about (90.7%) of the study area, and the spatial spread of this type is more than the rest of the other types of stability within the region.

We conclude from the above that the study area is located close to the linear structures not more than 1.3 km distance; Because of the number of linear structures distributed throughout the region and the largest part at the Euphrates River and Haditha Lake made them responsible for the meanders of the Euphrates River in the region, which caused unstable areas, and because they are areas of geological weakness, and thus the materials move on their slopes; Which causes a danger to its inhabitants, unlike areas far from linear structures.

Map (5) of the stability of linear structures in the study area

Source: Based on the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30×30 m) and the satellite visual (Land Sat 8) for the year 2019 AD and using the programs (Arc GIS10.8), (Erdas8.4) and (Geomatica 2015).

Table (3) Types of linear structures stability, their area and percentage

Types of stability	distance from linear structures	space km ²	Percentage %
Unstable areas	1.3	114.6	3.6
Semi-stable areas	1.3 – 2.7	183.2	5.7
Stable areas	2.8 and more	2916.6	90.7
Total		3214.36 km ²	100%

Source: Based on Map (5) and using Arc GIS10.8 software.

Third: Height characteristics:

Through the analysis of Map (6) and Table (4), we note the variation in altitude in the study area between (76-280) meters above sea level, and accordingly, the area was divided into five elevation categories as follows:

- The first category: (76 - 130) meters: the space of this category amounted to (288.6) km², about (9%) of the total area that spreads at the main valleys outlet, the Euphrates River and it's flood plain within the region. The map of elevations and the map of Geological structures show that these areas were affected by linear structures, and we can see this through the meanders of the Euphrates River in the study area; Because of it's influence by the linear structures. These structures are areas of geological weakness (breaks, cracks) so that the river has chosen these areas to pass through.
- The second category: (131 - 178) meters: it spreads in the areas following the flood plain of the Euphrates River in the middle of the region, and the area it occupies is (314.46) km², about (9.8%) of the total area.
- The third category: (179-208) meters: This category extends in the northern and southern parts of the region, about (19.2%) and an area of (617.3) km² of the total area.
- The fourth category (209 - 236) meters: it formed an area of (998.4) km², about (31.1%) of the total area that spreads in the part that follows the third category.
- Fifth category (237 - 280) meters: It is the highest category and occupies an area of (995.6) km², about (30.9%) of the total area, and it is spread in the northwestern and southwestern sides of the study area.

Map (6) of the elevation levels in the study area

Source: Based on the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30×30) m and using Program (Arc GIS10.8).

Table (4) The levels of heights for the categories, their areas (km²) and their percentage of the area (%) Source: Based on map (6).

Slope degrees	Classification	Area km ²	Percentage %	Landform
0 – 1.9°	flat land	752.3	23.4	flat land
2 – 4.9°	Simple slope	1336.9	41.6	Plain lands

5 - 9.9°	Slight slope	684.86	21.3	Rolling lands
10-18°	Moderate slope	440.3	13.7	Steep lands
Total	4 slope units	3214.36	100%	-

Fourth: The slope:

For the purpose of measuring the slope degrees, a digital elevation model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30 × 30) m was used for the Landsat satellite and a topographic map of the region using the (Arc GIS10.8) and (Global mapper12) program. The study adopted a classification (Young, 1975) in classifying slope categories. The study area was classified into four slope units, according to (Young, 1975) (1) classification, which are as follows:-

-The first category (0- 1.9°): These sloping surfaces are a result of weathering and erosion above the surface of the earth. These slopes represent the flat areas of the flood plain of the Euphrates River and the flat parts of the western plateau and Aljazira region, with an area of (752.3) km² and about (23.4%), see map (7) and table (5)

-The second category (2 - 4.9): has an area of (1336.9) km² with a rate of (41.6%), and these lands are characterized by the presence of weathering and erosion residues on the land, and these lands are a suitable place for human activities such as agriculture, buildings and road construction, and they provide drainage opportunities good for groundwater.

-The third category (5 - 9.9): It has an area of (684.86) km² and a rate of (21.3%). It is a land with a slight slope, and it has a good drainage of groundwater, and the processes of weathering and erosion are active in it.

-The fourth category (10-18): It is considered one of the steepest categories in the region, with an area of (440.3 km²), i.e. a rate of (13.7%), and it suffers from the activity of water erosion processes on its slopes.

Map (7) degrees of slopes in the study area

Source: Based on the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30×30) m and using the (Arc GIS10.8) program.

Table (5) slopes Classification; their Degrees, Areas (km²) and percentage (%) according to (Young, 1975) Classification

Source: Relying on:

1-Analysis of the digital elevation model (DEM) with a discriminatory accuracy of (30×30) m using the program (Arc GIS10.8).

2- Taghlib Gerges Daoud, Applied landform science (Applied Geomorphology), Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, Al-Mustansiriya University, College of Education, University House for Printing, Publishing and Translation, Basra, 2002, p. 121.

We conclude that the diversity of slope degrees is a result of the geomorphological work of the Euphrates River and the valleys sloping from the western plateau and the Jazira plateau towards the Euphrates river during the Pleistocene and Holocene periods, and the dry climate that developed these slopes through mechanical weathering processes, which is helped by the lack of vegetation cover, In addition to the impact of human activities and the alteration of slopes, a correlation was generated in the increase of some geomorphological features through the removal of some rock detectors, which helps to increase the activity of morphodynamic processes (movement of surface materials) on those slopes.

Fifth: The natural vegetation:

It is clear from the map (8) and table (6) that there are three categories of natural vegetation, and the study of natural vegetation in geomorphological studies, especially the risks, is not in determining the types of natural vegetation within the region; Rather, it is represented by its density within the study areas, which areas with high density, so the researcher studied the vegetation coverage coefficient (NDVI), which is extracted through the bands of the satellite visuals of the study area according to the following equation:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$$

Since:

NIR = Infrared band (Band 5) on Landsat 8

=RED Infrared band (Band 4) on Landsat 8

Through the results of the equation, we conclude the following:-

1- zero-density or barren areas: their area reached (1889.89) km², about (58.8%) of the study area, which is locate within a steep slope and residential areas, see map (8) and table (3-2).

2-Moderate density areas: their area reached (40.7) km², about (1.3%) of the study area, which is locate in the Banat Al-Hassan valley and Haqlan valley, and the areas confined between the low-density and the high-density areas.

3-Low-density areas: their area reached (1283.7) km², about (39.9%) of the study area, which is locate in the bottom of valleys such as Dulaq and Zagdan vallies and some scattered places within the study area.

Map (8) Density of Vegetation Cover (NDVI) in the study area

Source: Depending on the satellite visualization of the study area 8 (Land Sat) and using the programs (Erdas Imagine 14) and (Arc GIS10.8).

Table (6) Density of vegetation cover (NDVI) in the study area

Density type	NDVI value	Area (km ²)	Percentage of area %
Low	0.01 – 0.1	1283.7	39.9
Medium	0.1 – 0.2	40.7	1.3
Zero	0.3 - 0.4	1889.96	58.8
Total	-	3214.36	100%

Source: Depending on map (8).

Sixth: Building a model for the geomorphological risks of morphodynamic processes:

Through the layers that were previously produced, it became possible to build a mathematical model to determine the degrees of geomorphological risks for morphodynamic processes based on modern technologies represented in the (Arc GIS10.8) program by using the Arc Toolbox and then click on the (Spatial Analyst Tools)) From it we click on (Reclass) and then click on (Reclassify) to classify each layer into three categories, then we choose the Analysis Tools Spatial tool, then we choose the Map Algebra tool, and then we choose the Raster Calculator to give a value to each layer from Classes according to their effect on the degree of risk, see Table (7).

The layers entered into the geographic information system and making a model for geomorphological risks in the program(Arc GIS10.8) to determine the degrees of risk in the study area; this process requires identifying the layers that fall within the model in the geographic information system, which represent factors negatively affecting the occurrence of geomorphological risks in region, which are:

- 1-Geological formations.
- 2-Linear structures.
- 3-Height above sea level.
- 4-slope degree.
- 5- Natural vegetation.

Table (7) the weighted values to build a model of the geomorphological risks for the morphodynamic processes of the study area

Changing weight value	Changing class	Weighted value	Type	)Layers(	
1	Trio-time	30	Prevalence	geological formations	1
2	Quadric-time				
1	Less density	15	Density	Linear structures	2
2	Moderate density				
3	Extra density				
1	Unstable	15	Stability		
2	Medium stable				
3	stable				
1	Less height	15	Height	Above see level height	3
2	Medium height				
3	More height				
1	Flat- simple slope	15	Angle	Slope degree	4
2	Slight- moderate slope				
3	steep				
1	Less density	10	Density	Natural vegetation	5
2	Moderate density				
3	Zero density				

Source: Based on maps (2, 3, 6, 7, 8) and using Arc GIS10.8.

Map (9) and Table (8) show that there are three levels of risk that vary in their areas and degree of risk.

Map (9) model of geomorphological risks in the study area

Source: Based on maps (2, 3, 6, 7, 8) and using Arc GIS10.8 software.

Table (8) risks categories, their areas and percentage in the study area

risks categories	Area km2	Percentage %
High-risk areas	72.26	2.2
Medium-risk areas	2654.4	82.6
Low-risk areas	487.7	15.2
Total	3214.36	100%

Source: Based on map (9) and using Arc GIS10.8 software.

It clear that the areas of high risk were concentrated in the north of the region and in other areas, with an area of (72.26) km² and about (2.2%), which is the least in area, while areas of medium risk are spread in the north and south of the Euphrates River with an area of (2654.4). km², about (82.6%), which is the highest level of risks, while the areas of low risk came with an area of (487.7) km², about (15.2%) and are spread on both sides of the Euphrates River.

Seventh: Analysis of the impact of geomorphological risks on humanactivities:

The study of geomorphological risks is important in applied geomorphological studies; This is because of their significant and clear impact on various human activities. Geomorphological studies help in identifying and evaluating the type of geomorphological risks to which different regions are exposed. Which helps to clarify the procedures followed to reduce its destructive and environmental effects, and that geomorphological studies aim to demonstrate the suitability of the Earth's surface for human by evaluating it and identifying the risks that may occur in it due to natural and human factors. Therefore, the impact of geomorphological risks on human activities in the study area will be analyzed as follows:

1-Human settlement:

The study area is considered one of the vital areas; Due to the presence of the Haditha Dam and Haditha Lake, as well as the Al-Tahadi power station, which in total provided job opportunities for large numbers of residents of that area, which led to an increase in human settlement.

We can see that the lands with low and medium risk occupied an area of (3142.1 km²) of the total area of the region, i.e. (97.8%), thus being one of the most suitable areas for the purposes of urban expansion, while the high-risk areas occupied an area of (72.26 km²) and included northern areas, in addition to separate areas, and thus it is less suitable area for the purposes of urban expansion, and infrastructure and facilities should not be built in it; In order to avoid high geological and morphological risks.

1- Agricultural activity:

The geomorphological risks have an impact on the agricultural activity in the study area; Because the area is characterized by the cultivation of some agricultural crops, including wheat and barley, depending on the rainfall, and there are some farms for grapes and vegetables that depend on irrigation by means. The areas on both sides of the Euphrates River with a low-risk are considered more suitable for cultivation than the rest of the other areas of the region.

2-Transportation methods:

It was found that the region varies in its topography on the basis of the height and slope of the surface, as well as its variation in the different geological formations and the variation of its suitability to choose the most appropriate location for the construction of transportation route. This is because of its importance for the development of the areas in which it passes because it represents a link among human settlements, as we see the presence of a group of roads that break through the area from the middle, which represent more validity as shown in the map (10), while the areas on both sides of the river are exposed to erosion; Because of the torrential torrents in the winter season, which are characterized by their speed from the source region to the downstream region; As a result of the steep gradient, which leads to cutting roads in those areas.

Map (10) Geomorphological risks to human settlement and transportation routes in the study area

Source: based on:

- Republic of Iraq, Ministry of Transport and Public Transport, Directorate of Roads and Bridges in Anbar Governorate, Road Map of Anbar Governorate, for the year 2021, scale 1:1000000.
- A topographic map of Iraq at a scale of 1:100000 for the year 1990, issued by the General association for area.
- A satellite image of the satellite (Landsat 8), captured on February 22, 2021.
- Program (Arc GIS10.8).
- The program (Google Earth).

Conclusions:

- 1-The possibility of relying on modern technologies in determining the levels of risk by building a mathematical model.
- 2-Variation of weak geological formations in the region, which led to a large number of fractures and separation surfaces, different directions and numbers of linear structures and surface characteristics, as well as the poverty of vegetation cover in the region, which led to varying levels of danger in the region.
- 3-It clear that there are three levels of danger, as the low-risk lands reached an area of (487.7 km²) and were spread on both sides of the Euphrates River, while the medium-risk areas reached (2654.4 km²), while the area of the most dangerous reached (72.26 km²).

Recommendations:

1-Avoiding the establishment of human activities in the most dangerous areas in order to avoid losses that may occur as a result of this.

2-It is possible to rely on modern technologies in building and designing a spatial database to facilitate the process of determining the most suitable lands for human use.

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